

Corporate Governance and its relation with the performance of Firms listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange

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Abstract:

Corporate governance is an important concept known for the growth of firms; the purpose of this study is to understand the relationship between the performances and governance of corporations listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). Corporate governance is judged through the size of the board, CEO and chairman duality, a number of NED's and a number of NED's out of total directors in audit committee while the performance of firms is calculated through 'Return of Assets (ROA)' and 'Earnings gained per Share (EPS).' For this purpose, secondary data is used and taken from 25 companies listed at PSX. The data collected for a period of 5 years from (2013-2017) and quantitative technique is used for data analysis. The results of the study revealed that there exists a significant relationship between the performance of firms (ROA & EPS) and corporate governance mechanisms except for CEO & chairman composition. On the other hand, the results of Johansen's co-integration test concluded that there is long run integration between the firm's performance and their governance. VECM disclosed that there exists recombination of co-integration between governance and firm performance after some disturbance, except Audit Committee NED's proportion. Granger causality test concluded the significant cause of CEO/Chairman duality on firm's performance rather other three corporate governance mechanisms. It is recommended that companies need to focus on CEO and chairman composition factor for enhancing performance.

Indexing Terms / Keywords: Board size, CEO/chairman composition, Non-Executive Directors, Audit Committee, VECM (Vector Error Correction Model)

INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance is not actively concerned as the very important factor for the growth of corporations. The term 'Corporate Governance' has been defined by many researchers differently. Kukah, Amidu, and Abor (2016) defined corporate governance as examinations of different activities of managers all over the company by the board members or board executives.

Fernandez (2015) explained that Corporate Governance arises as a result of distraction between the ownership of the company and its management in a way that it requires a committee that manages the business operations. Kajola and O (2008) defined the term of Corporate Governance as a tool of assuring that the firms are well run, and operations are being held very effectively. Many other researchers have defined the corporate governance that it is a matter that associated with the manner of financial resources which are available to the corporation that how they are well operated and use to meet the objectives and dream of the corporation.

Arora and Sharma (2016) revealed in their study that firms which comply with the guidance of corporate governance lead to achieving high market performance. There is an important need of study to participate in the current debate related to corporate governance. As explained by Misangyi and Acharya (2014) corporate governance mechanisms are multiple, and the effective working of these mechanisms lead to high profitability, as high market profit is obtained when both the internal and external evaluating are present.

There is a lack of proof on the relationship of Board composition and the firm's financial performance, and this still demands the study that how the composition of board lead to high financial performance. There is a very small positive relationship between board and performance (Kiel & Nicholson, 2003). The ownership structure, i.e., separation and composition of CEO and firm's chairman lead to a high effect on the performance of the firms that in solving the problems arises in between the owners and managers (Kato & Long, 2006).

As explained by Black, Jang, and Kim (2006) that all rules and regulations regarding the governance of corporations are already available for a very long time that how corporations should be governed that are listed in stock exchanges for their respective countries in which they are working, and all are restricted to the

limitations settled for every perspective. However, the governance of firms always remains as a matter of discussion that how it leads to achieving high performance. Different researchers like Andres and Valledado (2008); Kajola and O (2008); Salim and Dr. (2012); & Abdullah (2004) have tried to prove this discussion that how corporate governance mechanisms like board size, NED's proportion, and board compensation and performance link, etc. lead to reach specific performance level. Actually, it is always considered that whether the codes and methods, issued by securities and commissions, results in improving the corporate performance or not. This study also has participated in identifying the relationship of governance and performance of firms. The results of the study showed that corporate governance and performance are cointegrated with each other and have a positive relationship with respect to the growing of each other.

The objective of this study is to understand the relationship and cointegration exist between corporate governance and firm's performance by enhancing the research on this topic by studying in Pakistan. The basic intention of this study is to provide empirical evidence for enhancing the importance of the governance of firms. Therefore, the main research question of the study would be that "whether there exists any relationship and long run co-integration between firm performance and Corporate governance or not?". The mechanisms chosen for corporate governance evaluation include board size, CEO duality, no. of NED's and NED's proportion in Audit Committee, while for performance measure and evaluation 'ROA' and 'EPS' is used.

By using the sample data from 25 listed firms at PSX, with 125 observations which means data collected for each firm for five years (2013-2017), the results of the study through Johansen's Co-integration test concluded that firms' performance and corporate governance are positively related. Furthermore, the 2nd section of the study include the review of literature in the light of firm's performance and corporate governance mechanisms chosen, 3rd section covers the theoretical framework and hypothesis generated for the study, 4th section involves methodology and data analysis while the 5th & 6th section cover empirical results and limitation of study respectively.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Board of the company plays an important role in the development of a company. Whenever a company fails in its operations, the responsibility for the failure relies on its board. As described by Mishra and Mohanty (2014) that board of a company as a corporate governance measure is a tool for influencing the firm performance as a driver for value addition in the company. Aslam, Ahmad, Amin, Usman, and Arif (2018) gave the empirical evidence from the listed firms of Australia that the firm performance is directly associated with the governance of its matter.

Some studies have shown negativity towards the linkage of a firm's profitability and corporate governance. Evidence from the Malaysian firms proofed that the board of a company and other governance mechanisms have no significant influence on the profit maximization and corporate performance of firms of Malaysia (Ramli & Ramli, 2016). It is expected from the firms executive managers of different committees to double their responsibilities, to care for the shareholders' rights and to do the job of contractual relation in between the board and firms activities (Boumosleh, 2005).

BOARD SIZE

Brown and Caylor (2004) discussed in their study about firms performance enhancement that how firm performance can be enhanced through corporate governance, suggested that firms having a board size with the number of members from 6 to 15 can perform very high relatively to other conditions of board of other companies who have a large or small number of board. It argues that a number of board members from 6 to 15 is an ideal situation for every company's board. Eisenberg, Sundgren, and Wells (1998) and Mak and Kusnadi (2005) argued in their studies about the integration of market performance of a firm and the size of board present in the company that there is not any significant relationship exists in between these two. Aggarwal, Stulz, and Williamson (2007) have also argued in their research work after the study of Eisenberg, Sundgren, and Wells (1998) and Mak and Kusnadi (2005) that there is no significant correlation exists between the market worth/performance of the firm and the size of the board of companies listed.

Bhagat and Black (2002) concluded in their study about the presence of NED's in the board and the performance of firm that there is no relation between the firm's performance and a number of NED's in the board, the performance has been captured using four different measures. From the recent view on the governance code for Pakistan, it came to know that it has been restricted by the code that presence of executive directors in the firm must not be more than 75% out of total board and it is also appreciated in the code for increasing the number of Non-executive members in the board.

BOARD COMMITTEE

Board committees are a basis on which the whole board based. The role of board committees is very vital for the firm's effectiveness and market value. It is revealed that strong performance is mostly associated with those firms who have good committees structure on voluntarily basis (Jaggi, Allini, Macchioni, & Zampella, 2018).

The formation of an effective Audit committee in small, medium and large enterprises lead to a positive relationship in between the earnings capacity (firm performance) and board while the other mechanisms of corporate governance doesnot give any evidence for a positive relationship with firm performance and improved earning capacity (Christensen, Kent, Routledge, & Stewart, 2015). It is revealed that the Audit committee with an increased level of dependent directors of the board, lead to a decrease in a fair report issued by the audit committee (Hermawan, 2011). The audit committee in relation with the other mechanisms of corporate governance revealed in one of the emerging economies, i.e., UAE. that audit committee is positively related with board size and independent board while no significant relationship with CEO duality (Hassan, 2017).

The board of a firm cannot deal with whole operations individually, so the board diversity is necessary for handling different resources. Mainly the board forms three committees, i.e., Audit committee, Nomination Committee, and Remuneration Committee while sometimes there exists one more committee, i.e., Risk committee. in this study, from all these committees, Audit committee is used as a measure for corporate governance, so the literature is done for evaluation of audit committee. The purpose of the audit committee is to ensure the effectiveness of the extetnal audit party in their evaluation for assuring the quality reports to be submitted to the board.

CHAIRMAN & CEO DUALITY

By analyzing many studies on the composition and seperation of chief executive and chairman, it came to know that there describes no best situation regarding their duality and seperation. Because both of the situations have their own merits and demerits for firm's progress point of view and some theories of corporate governance support duality and some support their separate role. Jensen (1993) stated that organization which has CEO and chairman duality creates problems for the through the pass of essential information for the organization and may lead the organization to be listed in bad information flow.

FIRMS PERFORMANCE

Lists of studies have been made to determine the relationship between the governance of the firm and their capacity to perform in the market. Coleman, Adjasi, and Abor (2007); Gul, Sajid, Razzaq, and Afzal (2012); Gompers, Ishii, and Metrick (2003); Klapper and Love (2004); and Yermack (1996) showed different results based on their evaluation of companies for performances and governance relationship. Kajola S. O (2008) provides very little proofs regarding the mannered and sophisticated relation in between the firms and their governance that there is very less evidence that provides justification of positive relationship of governance with firm performance. Black and Bhagat (2002) and Charlie and David (2000) studied and proofed that there exists significant positive relationship between the governance and the firm's attained performance in the market that the firms who have achieved a high performance level of their expectation are governed very well mannerly. However, on the other hand, Morck, Shleifer, and Vishny (1988) argued that there is no significant relationship between the governance of firms and their market performance achieving their settled target.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

H1: There exists compelling significant relation between board size, no. of NED's, and Audit NED's proportion with Return on Assets.

H2: CEO/chairman duality has a cogent relationship with Return on Assets.

H3: Board size, no. of NED's, Audit NED's proportion has a significant relationship with Earnings per Share.

H4: There is a compelling relationship between CEO/chairman duality and Earnings per Share.

H5: Corporate governance has a long run co-integration with the performance of firms (ROA & EPS).

H6: There exists recombination of co-integration between Board size, NED's proportion, CEO Chairman Duality and firm performance after some disturbance.

H7: There exists recombination of co-integration between the proportion of NED's in Audit committee and firm performance after some disturbance.

H8: There is a significant cause of Board size, NED's proportion and Audit proportion on the firm's performance.

H9: There is a significant cause of CEO/Chairman duality on the firm's performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of the study is to examine the performance of firms listed in the Pakistan Stock Exchange. To examine, the performance of firms is linked with the governance of firms and data is collected through the site of the State Bank of Pakistan and Pakistan Stock Exchange. The secondary data is collected through the annual reports published online of listed firms. The quantitative analysis technique is used to determine the relationship between corporate governance and firm's performance. Panel data analysis is used to determine the results of the variables.

Table 1. Variables of the Study

VARIABLE	ACRONYMS IN THE STUDY	DESCRIPTION
Board size	BOARDSIZ	Total number of members
no. of NED's	NED'sPROP	The percentage of non-executive directors out of the total board.
CEO/Chairman duality	CeoChrmn	Assign zero (0) for the same head of CEO and Chairman Assign one (1) for different seats of CEO and Chairman
Audit committee	AuditPROP	The proportion of non-executives directors in audit committee out of the total number of NED's in the board.
Earnings per share (Amt.)	EPS	Profit after tax / total no. of ordinary shares
Return on Assets %	ROA	profit after tax / total assets of the company

DATA ANALYSIS**Empirical****Table 2. Descriptive Statistics**

VARIABLE	MEAN	STD.DEVIATION	SKEWNESS	KURTOSIS
ROA	10.5085	15.83799	1.706	5.553
EPS	21.5944	37.49313	3.578	14.096
BOARDSIZ	8.70	2.037	1.486	1.743
NED'sPROP	0.5978	0.14106	-0.098	-0.518
CeoChrmn	0.87	0.335	-2.254	3.131
AuditPROP	0.5143	0.16481	-0.817	0.941

The descriptive statistics are evaluated in order to check the data viability and goodness. As it is showing the mean value for ROA is 10.5085%, EPS is 21.59 which show average earning by each company on one issued share is Rs. 21.59. Furthermore, board size is 8.70, shows the average no. of members in the board is 8 which is quite good as recommended by different researchers in their study that effective board should consist of 7 to 8 members (Ruback & Jensen, 1983). NED's proportion is 0.59 which shows that averagely 59% of the board is consist of Non-Executives directors, 0.87 mean value of CEO and Chairman showing that 87% companies of the board have one person performing the role of both CEO and Chairman. Audit proportion's mean value is showing that 51.14% of members in audit committees are Non-Executive directors.

Table 3. Pearson Correlation

Table 3.1 (ROA as a performance measure) Correlations

		BOARDSIZ	NEDsPROP	CeoChrmn	AuditPROP
ROA	Pearson Correlation	.054	.075	-.111	.299
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.275	.203	.108	.000
	N	125	125	125	125

The results of Pearson correlation of ROA with governance mechanisms showing that Return on Assets has a weak positive relationship with three mechanisms of governance, i.e., Board size, NED’s proportion, and Audit Prop as Pearson value is in positive but less than 1, however the CEO and Chairman duality’s negative value showing negative relationship of ROA with it.

Table 3.2 (EPS as a performance measure) Correlations

		BOARDSIZ	NEDsPROP	CeoChrmn	AuditPROP
EPS	Pearson Correlation	.085	.029	-.080	.213
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.174	.375	.189	.009
	N	125	125	125	125

The results of Pearson correlation of EPS with governance mechanisms showing that Earnings per Share have weak positive relationship with three mechanisms of governance, i.e., Board size, NED’s proportion, and Audit Prop as Pearson value is in positive but less than 1, however the CEO and Chairman duality with negative value showing negative relationship of EPS with it.

Table 4. Johansen Cointegration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE (s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.281215	139.1415	95.75366	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.238951	99.51834	69.81889	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.163235	66.75145	47.85613	0.0003
At most 3 *	0.154678	45.36595	29.79707	0.0004
At most 4 *	0.106095	25.20143	15.49471	0.0013
At most 5 *	0.093220	11.74270	3.841466	0.0006

Trace test indicates 6 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE (s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.281215	39.62320	40.07757	0.0562
At most 1	0.238951	32.76689	33.87687	0.0674
At most 2	0.163235	21.38550	27.58434	0.2536
At most 3	0.154678	20.16452	21.13162	0.0678
At most 4	0.106095	13.45873	14.26460	0.0667
At most 5 *	0.093220	11.74270	3.841466	0.0006

Max-eigenvalue test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Johansen Co integration becomes capable of testing the variables when the variables contain a stationary process, as checking the stationarity of the variables is an assumption for this test. In this study, the stationarity of variables is tested through the unit root, and all variables become stationary at level. The Trace and Maximum Eigen Value are two forms of Johansen to test the co-integration among variables:

Trace test for $K_0 = 0$

Maximum Eigenvalue test for $K_0 = m-1$

In case, these two forms vary with one and each other, so the results of the trace should opt. In this study, trace results of 6 co-integrating equations showing the probability value of F-test less than 0.05 with significant(positive) F-(critical value), so the null hypothesis is rejected in the way and there exists the strategic co-integration among the variables. While the Maximum Eigen results of 6 co-integrating equations showing the probability value of F-test more than 0.05 with insignificant F-(critical value), so the null hypothesis is accepted in the way and there neither exist strategic co-integration among the variables.

By considering the condition of this test of accepting one form in case of differentiation of results, we accept the Trace results that there is a significant co-integration between the performance of firms and corporate governance.

Table 5. Vector Error Correction Model

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1
EPS(-1)	1.000000
ROA(-1)	0.181850 (0.52886) [0.30682]
AUDITPRO(-1)	-85.21059 (53.5829) [-1.59026]
BOARDSIZ(-1)	-9.567609 (3.89085) [-2.45900]
CEOCHRMN(-1)	182.6145 (27.0152) [6.75969]
NEDSPROP(-1)	148.2849 (57.6410) [2.57256]
C	-143.2779

Error Correction:	D(EPS)	D(ROA)	D(AUDITPRO)	D(BOARDSIZ)	D(CEOCHR...	D(NEDSPR...
Constant	0.001015 (0.04675) [-4.81140]	0.017410 (0.02493) [-0.68759]	0.000000 (0.00031) [0.71453]	0.000104 (0.00269) [-0.06826]	0.000000 (0.00058) [-5.57348]	0.000000 (0.00023) [-2.59798]
D(EPS(-1))	0.052939 (0.10059) [0.52630]	0.014119 (0.05364) [0.26322]	0.000341 (0.00067) [0.51067]	0.000739 (0.00579) [0.12773]	0.002231 (0.00126) [1.77589]	0.000567 (0.00050) [1.14090]
D(EPS(-2))	0.104166 (0.10051) [1.03632]	0.077306 (0.05360) [1.44231]	0.000287 (0.00067) [0.43059]	0.003332 (0.00578) [0.57603]	0.001185 (0.00126) [0.94360]	0.000210 (0.00050) [0.42198]
D(ROA(-1))	-0.001343 (0.20210) [-0.00664]	0.127956 (0.10777) [1.18733]	0.000336 (0.00134) [0.25061]	-0.006941 (0.01100) [-0.59677]	-0.000517 (0.00252) [-0.20488]	-0.000458 (0.00100) [-0.45796]
D(ROA(-2))	-0.200230 (0.20158) [-0.99332]	-0.324870 (0.10749) [-3.02235]	-0.001240 (0.00134) [-0.92590]	-0.001287 (0.01160) [-0.11098]	0.004827 (0.00252) [1.91724]	0.001802 (0.00100) [1.80800]
D(AUDITPRO(-1))	-17.20796 (15.3041) [-1.12440]	-17.41873 (8.16083) [-2.13443]	-0.492634 (0.10164) [-4.84675]	-0.282377 (0.88071) [-0.32063]	-0.214720 (0.19114) [-1.12339]	-0.023189 (0.07566) [-0.30651]
D(AUDITPRO(-2))	-4.701167 (15.0982) [-0.31137]	7.808721 (8.05099) [0.96991]	-0.129237 (0.10027) [-1.28884]	-0.131110 (0.86885) [-0.15090]	-0.157500 (0.18856) [-0.83527]	-0.111905 (0.07464) [-1.49931]
D(BOARDSIZ(-1))	-2.124951 (1.76883) [-1.20100]	-0.753520 (0.94322) [-0.79999]	-0.000381 (0.01175) [-0.03244]	-0.039163 (0.10179) [-0.38474]	-0.036726 (0.02209) [-1.66290]	0.001676 (0.00874) [-0.13108]
D(BOARDSIZ(-2))	-2.087421 (1.70127) [-1.17188]	1.191851 (0.34900) [1.25478]	-0.005644 (0.01100) [-0.47711]	-0.122287 (0.10225) [-1.19296]	0.011982 (0.02209) [0.53858]	0.000365 (0.00000) [0.04150]
D(CEOCHRMN(-1))	23.72173 (7.84832) [3.02252]	2.187485 (4.18507) [0.52269]	-0.032968 (0.05212) [-0.63248]	-0.080423 (0.45165) [-0.17807]	0.232904 (0.09802) [2.37611]	0.025527 (0.03880) [0.65793]
D(CEOCHRMN(-2))	21.76236 (7.60112) [2.86305]	3.861381 (4.05325) [0.95266]	-0.021073 (0.05048) [-0.41744]	-0.321290 (0.43742) [-0.73451]	-0.083353 (0.09493) [-0.87803]	0.040526 (0.03758) [1.07849]
D(NEDSPROP(-1))	32.56553 (19.9706) [1.71667]	-1.816606 (4.04467) [-0.17958]	-0.161346 (0.18600) [-1.28062]	-0.013935 (1.00100) [-0.01276]	0.279749 (0.09802) [1.18077]	-0.094683 (0.00376) [-1.00963]
D(NEDSPROP(-2))	21.83231 (19.0408) [1.14661]	-5.686715 (10.1534) [-0.56008]	0.179938 (0.12646) [1.42289]	-1.583468 (1.09574) [-1.44511]	0.066942 (0.23780) [0.28150]	-0.206487 (0.09413) [-2.19367]
C	0.064849 (2.21702) [0.02924]	0.281718 (1.10220) [0.23823]	0.006632 (0.01470) [0.45029]	0.002806 (0.12702) [0.02199]	0.000459 (0.02770) [0.01658]	0.002322 (0.01000) [0.21179]

R-squared	0.199623	0.149601	0.254831	0.059757	0.368937	0.159032
Adj. R-squared	0.103281	0.047238	0.165135	-0.053420	0.292975	0.057804
Sum sq. resid	64733.47	18406.86	2.855341	214.3754	10.09701	1.581983
S.E. equation	24.48232	13.05503	0.162599	1.408885	0.305763	0.121029
F-statistic	2.072032	1.461481	2.841046	0.527994	4.856903	1.571031
Log likelihood	-555.8253	-479.1144	55.93412	-207.4967	-21.11183	91.95537
Akaike AIC	9.341398	8.083843	-0.687445	3.631093	0.575604	-1.277957
Schwarz SC	9.663171	8.405616	-0.365672	3.952866	0.897377	-0.956184
Mean dependent	0.012623	0.212377	0.004918	0.000000	0.000000	0.002049
S.D. dependent	25.85380	13.37476	0.177954	1.372697	0.363636	0.124686

Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)	4.389568
Determinant resid covariance	2.112542
Log likelihood	-1084.284
Akaike information criterion	19.25056
Schwarz criterion	21.31910

Vector Error Correction Model is a test generated in order to find out the correction for the error which may occur in the cohesion of variables. This is a kind of forecasting method for examining the recombining of co-integration exists among the variables. For this test, there must be a co-integration exist in variables and containing the stationary process among them. So after checking the stationarity and testing the Co-integration through Johansen test, we are capable of applying VECM (vector error correction model). The results of the

study showing that to anticipate the long term co-integration in the variables, the coefficient terms of all variables are in negative value and have a significant F-test probability value (less than 0.05), so it can say that after the disturbance occurred in the co-integration of performance and corporate governance, the relation will get back to its position after sometime — all variables are having a negative coefficient term and positive F-test value except the proportion of NED’s in Audit committee with the positive coefficient term (0.000222),(0.71453) showing that after disturbance the co-integration existing with the performance of the firm will not get back to its position.

Table 6. Granger Causality Test

Null Hypothesis is:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob
EPS does not Granger cause AUDITPRO	125	0.85952	0.6041
AUDITPRO does not Granger cause EPS		0.50283	0.9252
ROA does not Granger cause AUDITPRO	125	1.52720	0.1197
AUDITPRO does not Granger cause ROA		1.55015	0.1119
EPS does not Granger cause BOARDSIZ	125	3.68674	9.E-05
BOARDSIZ does not Granger cause EPS		0.59906	0.8584
ROA does not Granger cause BOARDSIZ	125	0.93813	0.5227
BOARDSIZ does not Granger cause ROA		0.79702	0.6697
EPS does not Granger cause CEOCHRMN	125	2.04983	0.0235
CEOCHRMN does not Granger cause EPS		1.71692	0.0677
ROA does not Granger cause CEOCHRMN	125	1.44213	0.1529
CEOCHRMN does not Granger cause ROA		1.62621	0.0893
EPS does not Granger cause NEDSPROP	125	1.29724	0.2272
NEDSPROP does not Granger cause EPS		0.60625	0.8526
ROA does not Granger cause NEDSPROP	125	1.59735	0.0973
NEDSPROP does not Granger cause ROA		0.28845	0.9940

The granger causality test and vector error correction model are approached after the existence of co-integration among the variables. When there are stationarity and co-integration exists in the variables, both of these can be applied. The granger test tells us about the change in one variable of the study due to the other variable. Two major constructs for the study are the firm’s performance and corporate governance. The granger causality test applied in order to find out the cause of change in one variable by the other. So the results of this test show that all null hypothesis developed for the test is accepted as all having insignificant F-test value with more than 0.05 probability measure means they are not causing one and each other except the one hypothesis which is for CEO and chairman duality. The cause of governance measures, i.e., NED’s proportion, board size, and proportion of NED’s in audit committees did not cause by and caused to ROA and EPS, while CEO and chairman duality do cause by and cause to ROA and EPS. The null hypothesis developed for the test can only be accepted in the case if probability value is more than 0.05 so, in this study, all hypotheses are accepted except the hypothesis developed for CEO and chairman duality.

RESULTS

HYPOTHESIS	RESULTS
H1: There exists compelling significant relation between board size, no. of NED's, and Audit NED's proportion with Return on Assets.	ACCEPTED
H2: CEO/chairman duality has a cogent relationship with Return on Assets.	REJECTED
H3: Board size, no. of NED's, Audit NED's proportion has a significant relationship with Earnings per Share.	ACCEPTED
H4: There is a compelling relationship between CEO/chairman duality and Earnings per Share.	REJECTED
H5: Corporate governance has a long run co-integration with the performance of firms (ROA & EPS).	ACCEPTED
H6: There exists recombination of co-integration between Board size, NED's proportion, CEO Chairman Duality and firm performance after some disturbance.	ACCEPTED
H7: There exists a recombination of co-integration between the proportion of NED's in Audit committee and firm performance after some disturbance.	REJECTED
H8: There is a significant cause of Board size, NED's proportion and Audit proportion on the firm's performance.	REJECTED
H9: There is a significant cause of CEO/Chairman duality on the firm's performance.	ACCEPTED

CONCLUSIONS

The main motivation behind the conduction of this study was to find out the relationship and co-integration in between the corporate governance and performance of firms listed at Pakistan Stock Exchange. The major findings of the study revealed that corporate governance mechanisms (board size, NED's proportion, CEO and chairman duality and No. of NED's in audit committee) have a significant relationship with firms performance (ROA and EPS). Pearson results show that board size, NED's proportion, and No. of NED's in audit committee have a positive correlation with ROA and EPS while CEO and chairman duality have a negative correlation with ROA and EPS. The results of Johansen Co-integration revealed strong co-integration exists between governance and firm's performance. The results of Vector error correction which becomes applicable after Johansen divulged that after some disturbance there is a recombination of co-integration between Board size, NED's proportion, CEO Chairman Duality and ROA & EPS (firms performance), EXCEPT the variable of the proportion of NED's in Audit committee. The Granger test unveiled about the cause of CEO and chairman duality on firm performance (ROA & EPS), while rest of the three governance measures does not cause to the firms' performance.

IMPLICATIONS

By considering the conclusions, it is recommended that to improve the firm's performances, governance mechanisms are so important to manage while making their policies as they have long run co-integration with ROA & EPS as unveiled by Johansen's Co-integration test. Granger results suggested that companies should focus more on the CEO and chairman duality as it is the only factor causing the ROA & EPS in the study and it only has negative correlation with ROA & EPS revealed by Pearson's correlation test, i.e., if CEO and chairman's role are performed by two different individuals, the performance of firms will be negatively affected

as 87% of firms have same CEO & Chairman. Governance mechanisms are so important to manage as they have long run co-integration with ROA & EPS as unveiled by Johansen's Co-integration test.

Limitations and Recommendations

This study is limited to a few variables of corporate governance; the future researchers may add more governance related variables for the expansion of this current topic. The current topic consisting of corporate governance and firm performance is highly motivated to be done qualitatively for doing it differently. Future researchers may expand this topic by adding moderating and mediating variables in the study. It may be explored by comparing with the other stock markets of competitive countries or around the world.

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